

Review Article

G-D's Physics' Novel Computational Definition of "Mass" Unifies Between GRT & QM, as well as the Four Forces!

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Note: Dr. Bentovish is affiliated with Zefat Academic Center and Ariel University. He is now calling the leading Astronomers and Cosmologists in the world to collaborate with him to further validate the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm. Dr. Bentovish (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics has reached a state of a "Paradigmatic Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm of GRT & QM – towards the New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, based on its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that continuously (and "simultaneously") computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's Four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec⁻¹ thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "Minimal Time Pont"! Based on empirical validation of two (unique) "G-D's Physics" "Critical Predictions": its "UNCIARE-JRH" & "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated findings – as more accurate than the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's GRT & QM, "G-D's Physics" is accepted as the New Twenty-First Century Physics Paradigm! Consequently, it completely revises Science's basic conception and understanding of the origin (and age) of the universe, its essential nature and basic dynamics! The "new" universe is understood to be continuously "computed"- "dissolved" re-computed"- and "developed"- singularly by this higher-ordered UCP, leading it towards an "Ultimate Perfected Geulah" State in which Science and Humanity will realize the UCP's singularity, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality" Peace" & "Harmony" (that will therefore also characterize Humanity's existence & behavior!) Indeed, the current discovery and empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm result in a complete unification of GRT & QM, the Four Physical Features & the Four Forces (for the first time in Physics!) A prospective Call for all Astronomers & Experimental Physicists is made to validate two additional (breakthrough) unique "Critical Predictions" of this New "G-D's Physics", likely to alter the face of 21st Century Physics in the same manner that Eddington's validation of GRT forever changes 20th Century Physics!

Introduction

According to Thomas Kuhn's (well-known and widely accepted) analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" (1962) has taught us in what manner Science (in any given subdiscipline) develops, and what may be the general "sequence of events" that inevitably lead any given Scientific subdiscipline towards transcending any given Old ("standard") Scientific Paradigm towards the discovery of a broader New Scientific Paradigm (NSP). The preceding "marks" for such a "Paradigmatic-Shift" (in any given scientific sub-discipline) is the appearance of a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" signified by:

a) An intrinsic "theoretical-inconsistency" between the "pillars" of the Old Standard Paradigm (e.g., such as the basic "theoretical inconsistency" that existed between Newtonian Classical Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory prior to Einstein's 1905's discovery of Relativity Theory).

b) A Principle inability of that Old Standard Paradigm to account for a key major empirical phenomenon (e.g., such as the principle inability of the Old Standard Paradigm of Newton's Classical Mechanics to account for the "Ether" hypothetical concept that was assumed to perfuse the entire physical universe, but could not be detected despite numerous experimen-

tal efforts to do so).

Currently, Science is undergoing such a "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm, e.g., underlying both GRT and QM to the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, also signified by such a preceding "Paradigmatic-Crisis" typified by:

a) An intrinsic (apparent) "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM, i.e., which stems from:

1. An apparent contradiction between GRT's insistence upon the "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) for the transmission of any signal (or even information) across space and time – and QM's (empirically verified) "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon (which suggests that a measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects and determines the other "entangled particle's" "complimentary-pair" values: even though these two entangled particles are separated by a distance greater than can be traversed by a light signal!?)

2. An apparent inability to unify between GRT's "Gravitational Force" and the other "Three Forces" (e.g., Electromagnetic, Weak & Strong Nuclear Forces); Interestingly, these other Three Forces have been unified by QM's

Standard Model, which explains each of these other Three Forces based on a the "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) direct physical interactions of certain subatomic particles. In contrast, GRT's account of the (fourth) "Gravitational Force" does not rely on any such direct physical interactions between elementary subatomic particles. In addition, this "Gravitational Force" is assumed to travel at the Speed of Light!?

b) A (principle) inability of the Old MCR Paradigm to account for two key empirical phenomena:

1. The accelerated expansion of the universe, i.e., "Hubble's Tension": As known, recently there arose an unexplained "gap" between the universe's (early) "Cosmological" (e.g., "Background Radiation") and (contemporary) significantly increased "Astronomical" Measures of the universe's rate of expansion***! This "unexplained" "Hubble's Tension" – cannot be accounted for (satisfactorily) through GRT's assumed (purely hypothetical) "Dark Matter" (DM) concept: e.g., assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but which could not be detected experimentally for the past two full decades (despite numerous efforts to do so?!). Even beyond the experimental failure to detect the existence of this (purely hypothetical) DM concept; But, even if this (purely hypothetical) DM concept existed (somehow) – it could not account for the accelerated expansion of the universe, i.e., "Hubble's Tension"! This is because even if such (purely hypothetical) DM concept existed (somehow), it could only account for a "constant rate" of the universe's expansion (because its finite material quantity would remain, at best, constant or even decrease over time!?) Therefore, the Old MCR's GRT's assumption of the purely hypothetical DM concept cannot (satisfactorily) account for the empirically observed gap in the accelerated expansion of the universe, e.g., "Hubble's Tension"!

2. The "Proton-Radius Puzzle": Another key "unexplained" empirical phenomenon related to the QM's (principle) inability to account for the "smaller diameter"- and "more accurate measurement"- of the Hydrogen's Proton: when taken from an "altered Hydrogen" Atom in which the negatively charged electron has been replaced by a much more massive (e.g., roughly 100 times more massive) "Muon" particle (i.e., relative to the Hydrogen's Proton Radius in a "standard" Hydrogen Atom, which is encircled by the negatively charged electron). ****

Following Kuhn's (brilliant) analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions", It becomes apparent that in order for Science to accept (and embrace) a New Scientific Paradigm (NSP), it is necessary for any such NSP to be able to:

a) Resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistencies" between GRT & QM.

3. Offer an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the (otherwise) "unexplained" phenomenon of the universe's accelerated of expansion:

4. Identify at least one (unique) "Critical Prediction" that can differentiate this NSP from the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's GRT & QM!

5. To the extent that even one(unique) "Critical Prediction" of this NSP is empirically proven to be more accurate than the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's GRT or QM – then this must (inevitably) lead to the (unequivocal) acceptance of this NSP, as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century Physics!

Methods& Results

order to directly contrast between the new "G-D'S PHYSICS" Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-D'S PHYSICS" identified two unique "Critical-Prediction" relating to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" (New Year's) time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCP; According to the Old ("Material-Causal") GRT's Paradigm, the (purely hypothetical concept of) DM predicts a "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion – i.e., which should not increase over time! In contrast, according to one of the new Theoretical Postulates of the "G-D'S PHYSICS" termed: The "Collective

Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH), whenever there is a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), e.g., of a large group of human-beings focusing upon this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), this results in an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" ("UNCIARE")! For example, during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana's" (new year) two days' special time-interval, according to the CUFT (unique) "UNCIARE-JRH" "Critical Prediction", there should be measured a "non-continuous increase" in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., predicted to occur during the JRH's two days special annual interval of a CHCF!)

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

Pohl [27-29] set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Confirmation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction

In order to confirm "G-D's Physics" (unique) "UNCIARE (JRH)" Critical Prediction it is necessary to gauge and compare the rate of the universe's expansion – at it's early (Cosmological) stages, as opposed to the current (Astronomical) measure of the universe's rate of expansion: Once again, according to "G-D's Physics" (unique) UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction, the rate of the universe's expansion increases at every year's JRH's CHCF (two days' special time interval – e.g., at which Millions of Jew collectively focus on this singular higher-ordered UCP!), hence predicted to lead to an overall increase in the rate of the universe's expansion from its early Cosmological measure to the current Astronomical measure of the universe's expansion rate! (As indicated above, this unique "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction predicting an overall increase in the universe's expansion rate from its early Cosmological to the current Astronomical rate of expansion – stands in stark contrast to the Old MCR's GRT's purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" prediction regarding the rate of the universe's expansion which should remain **constant over time!?**)

Indeed, the "Hubble's Tension" [34], empirical findings (unequivocally) supports "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH prediction regarding such an increase in the rate of the universe's expansion – from the universe's initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec –

as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion [34-40]?! In other words, "G-D's Physics" unique UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction, predicting that the Universe's expansion rate will increase (annually) during every consecutive JRH's two days' (special) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – is validated by the "Hubble's Tension" [34-40], findings! In contrast, these "Hubble's Tension" [34-40], findings cannot be explained by the current "Standard Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT, which assumes that the universe's accelerated expansion is the result of (purely hypothetical) "Dark Matter" concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe (but which failed to be detected despite twenty years of intensive experimentation attempting to do so)!? Even beyond that, even theoretically this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept could not account for the empirically observed "Hubble's Tension" [34-40], because such a (purely hypothetical) DM concept could only account for a constant-rate expansion of the universe (e.g., over time), but not for the "Hubble's Tension" [32-334-40], results indicating that the universe's rate of expansion increases over time, which precisely confirm "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction!

Likewise, the empirically measured "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings precisely support "G-D's Physics" novel UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given particle as function of its "Object Spatial Consistency" (across a series of UF's Frames); therefore the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the (relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen") than the (relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen") was predicted by "G-D's Physics" to lead to a "spatially-smaller"- and spatially more accurate"- measurement of that "Muon-Hydrogen" empirical findings! In contrast, these "Proton-Radius Puzzle" empirical findings could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" [49], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction [53,57], higher dimension gravity [48], a new boson [52], and the quasi-free hypothesis π^+ [51], and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm! Hence, these "Proton-Radius Puzzle" empirical results unequivocally support "G-D's Physics" unique Critical Prediction stemming from its (novel) UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given (subatomic) particle (or relativistic object)!

Discussion

The impressive (abovementioned) results indicating that "G-D's Physics" two (unique) "Critical Predictions": a) the UNCIARE-JRH Cumulative Increase in the Universe's Rate of Expansion! b) The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated findings; directly validate "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm as more valid than the Old MCR's GRT's & QM's corresponding predictions, thereby unequivocally validating "G-D's Physics" as the New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics!

1. G-D's Physics' New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm

In order to fully appreciate the basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" brought about by the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm we need to highlight the fundamental metamorphosis signified by "G-D's Physics" NSP, i.e., as an "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This is because the Old "Material-Causal Paradigm" (MCR) underlying both GRT & QM is characterized by its basic assumption: wherein it is assumed that any ("macroscopic") relativistic or ("subatomic") quantum physical phenomena (e.g., or entity, process etc.) – is "caused" by direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" ("random") physical interactions between a given set of "material" factors (or entities)! Thus, for instance, the basic MCR assumption underlying GRT assumes that the curvature of "Space-Time" is "caused" by the direct physical interaction between certain "massive objects" and their surrounding "Space-Time" which results in a "curved Space-Time" around these "massive material objective"; which (in turn) "Causes" (or

determines) the "travelling-pathways" of other "less-massive" objects around these "massive objects"! Likewise, the basic MCR assumption underlying QM is such that it is assumed that the determination of any given subatomic "target" particle's "probability wave-function's" properties are "caused" by its (direct) "material-causal" physical interaction with another corresponding "probe" entity – which "collapses" this "target's probability wave-function" into a singular (complimentary) value.

In contrast, given "G-D's Physics" discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), which **simultaneously** computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every (subsequent) "minimal time-point" (e.g., many "trillions" or times per second)! Then, this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is also considered as an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! This implies that since all of the exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe are **simultaneously** computed for each consecutive UF's frame/s, then there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given (subsequent) UF's frame/s! Likewise, this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Paradigm negates the possibility of the existence of any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – also across any two subsequent (or non-subsequent) UF's frame/s, because all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any (single) UF's frame/s "dissolve" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s! This implies that according to the New ACC "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (of Twenty-first Century Physics) there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising either the same- or different- (e.g., subsequent or even non-subsequent) UF's frame/s!

Indeed, this (novel) ACC "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm fundamentally revises (and in fact "metamorphosizes") our whole basic understanding of the origin- nature- dynamics- and development- of the entire physical universe (e.g., at both the "relativistic-macroscopic", and "subatomic-quantum" levels: No longer, can we accept the Old MCR basic "material-causal" assumption, wherein it is assumed that the universe was created (or "caused") by an initial ("random") nuclear event – which is assumed to "cause" the creation of Suns, galaxies atoms, "space", "time", "energy" and "mass" etc.!? This is because (as mentioned above and previously) since there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – either within any (single) UF's frame/s, or across any two (subsequent- or even non-subsequent) UF's frame/s; therefore, there could not have existed such a (purely hypothetical) "Big-Bang" nuclear explosion – because such an initially (GRT's assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear explosion is assumed to entail precisely such "material-causal" interaction/s between this "Big-Bang" nuclear explosion and its creation of those "Suns", "Galaxies", "mass", "energy", "space" and "time" etc.. But, based on "G-D's Physics" (newly discovered) ACC Paradigm, there could not have existed any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive-spatial pixels, e.g. existing in the "first", "second"... "trillionth" etc. UF's frame/s! Likewise, GRT's Old MCR's (basic) "material-causal" assumption wherein it is assumed that the whole dynamics, sustenance, and development of the entire physical universe is "caused" by the direct "material-causal" physical interaction/s between certain "massive" objects and other (relatively) "less-massive" objects which is assumed to "cause" the "curvature of Space-Time"; and this (assumed) "curved Space-Time" "causes" (or determines) the "travelling-pathways" of all "massive" and "less-massive" objects is also strictly negated by "G-D's Physics" New ACC Scientific Paradigm! Once again, based on G-D's Physics' ACC Paradigm's new understanding that there cannot exist any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal"

physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, therefore there cannot also exist any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between those "massive objects" and other "less-massive" objects – which "causes" the "curvature of Space-Time" (nor the determination of the "travelling-pathways" of these "massive" or other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by the "curvature of Space-Time"?!

2. G-D's Physics' Novell Computational Definition of the "Gravitational Force" Metamorphosizes "Space-Time" Curvature!

Instead, G-D's Physics' New ACC Scientific Paradigm explains GRT's "Gravitational Force" – not as "caused" by (certain) "massive objects" causing the "curvature of space-time" (i.e., which is negated by "G-D's Physics" new ACC Paradigm, as explained above); but rather through "G-D's Physics" (novel) UCP's computational definition of "Mass" (e.g., of any given subatomic particle or of any relativistic object) – as the degree of "Object-Consistent" presentations of any such "object" across a given series of UF's frames!

"Mass"

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - [O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i...n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

Surprisingly, this novel UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of

Figure 1: "G-D's Physics" Alternative Explanation for "Curved Space-Time"!

However, the great "elegance" of this New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (e.g., empirically proven to be more valid e.g., in two of its unique "Critical-Predictions" than the corresponding predictions of the Old "MCR": GRT & QM Paradigm); is that its novel computational definition of the UCP's computation of the "mass" value of any given (relativistic or quantum) "object" allows it to derive an altogether new alternative explanation for the apparent "curvature of Space-Time" by (certain) "massive" objects! Since (as mentioned above and previously), according to the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single (or even multiple) UF's (e.g., due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!); therefore this New ACC "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is shown capable of deriving an "appearance" of those "HMLE" (e.g., "large Red circle") "consistent regions" remaining relatively "stable" across a series of UF's frame/s, as opposed to the "inconsistent regions" of those "LMHE" (e.g., alternating "blue/white small circles")

any given (subatomic particle or relativistic) "object" offers an entirely new understanding of the "curvature of Space-Time", as well as of the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; which when taken together with the (simultaneous) UCP's computation of the other three Physical Features (for every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe!) allows "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm to completely unify (for the first time in Physics!) between those Four basic Physical Features, as well as between GRT & QM! Indeed, according to The New "G-D's Physics" UCF's simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic Physical Features creates (relatively) "consistent regions" (i.e., within a given "location" in the "coordinates" of the "Universal Frame" – across a series of UF's frames!): which may be characterized as "High-Mass; Low Energy" ("HMLE") "consistent regions, represented by the large "red" circles (in Figure 1); As opposed to other "Low-Mass; High-Energy" (LMHE) which appear as (relatively) "inconsistent-regions" (e.g., within a given "location" in the "coordinates" of the Universal Frame – across a series of UF's frames!); Hence, as we can see (in Figure 1) the UCP's computation of "differential consistency regions": a) The "HMLE" "consistent regions" of the "large Red circles", which remain "spatially-consistent" across the two UF's frames; as opposed to : b) The "LMHE" "inconsistent regions" of the "small (alternating) blue/white" which continuously "alternate" (i.e., are "spatially inconsistent") across the two illustrated UF's frames! This implies that those LMHE (alternating "blue/white circles") create a "vacuum" or an "empty-alternating space" around those "consistent" HMLE ("Red circle), thereby giving rise to the "appearance" of "curved Space-Time" around those HMLE "consistent Red circles"!

which produces a "vacuum" or "empty-space" around those "HMLE -consistent regions", thereby giving rise to the appearance of a "curved Space-Time" around those "HMLE" ("Red circle")!

3. "G-D's Physics" Complete Integration of GRT-QM & the Four Physical Features!

Strikingly, this new alternative ACC "G-D's Physics" theoretical account for the "appearance" of the "Relativistic curvature of Space-Time" by (certain) "massive objects" – which negates the very possibility of the existence of any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions, e.g., between any two (or more Relativistic or Quantum) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing either in the same- or other- UF's frames) "opens the door" for a complete unification between GRT & QM, as well as between GRT's "Gravitational Force" and QM's "Standard Model's" other Three (e.g., Electromagnetic, Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces)! This is simply because "G-D's Physics" the discovery of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP which "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' Four (basic) Physical Features, has also led to its discovery of a singular unified "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) which completely integrates between those Four Physical Features (i.e., as "secondary computational

by-products" of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle", "UCP") (Figure 2)!

FIGURE 2: The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...n} [Px] (a...z)

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

Wherein the UCP represented by the Hebrew Letter "י" computes at an extremely rapid rate, e.g., of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ (sec)" simultaneously every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising every consecutive UF's – including the UCP's complete integration of those Four basic Physical Features through the UCF's: $s * e / t * m$ computation (e.g., for each exhaustive spatial pixel – from "a to z")!

In order to see how this (novel) "G-D's Physics" Computational Definitions of each of the Four (basic) Physical Features is (fully) integrated within the UCF's singular formula – i.e., and which also allows for "G-D's Physics" complete integration of GRT & QM (as "special-cases" within the broader- exhaustive- higher-ordered theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" UCF!); let us examine "G-D's Physics" (novel) "Computational Definitions" of each of those Four (basic) Physical Features:

Indeed, "G-D's Physics" (novel) UCP's "Computational Definitions" of the Four Physical Features are based on the discovery of the UCP's two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" ("frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent"): wherein the UCP's computation of the UF's "frame" (level's) – "consistent" (e.g., "space") or "inconsistent" ("energy") Physical Features relates to the UCP's computation of the degree of "consistency" or "inconsistency" of any given "object", relative to the entire UF's ("coordinate-system", e.g., across a series of UF's frame/s)! Or, conversely, the UCP's computation of any given object's "object" (e.g., "internal-composition's) – "consistent" (e.g., "mass") or "inconsistent" (e.g., "time") produce the entire UF's exhaustive spatial pixels' Four basic Physical Features values! (See Figure 1).

The UCP's Four Physical Features (Novel) Computational Definitions: "Space"

S: $(f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots + f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$ such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) \leq f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i...n)]$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure! Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the

"Energy"

E: $(f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots - f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$
such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i...n)]$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's. In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes): $M: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n \{UF's(i...n)\}$ where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

"Mass"

M: $[O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i...n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"Time"

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

T: $\sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i...n)\} / c * n \{UF's(i...n)\}$ such that: $T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i...n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Table 1 illustrates the UCP's Computational Dimensions' derived Four (basic) Physical Features:

In order to illustrate the (full) integration of "G-D's Physics" singular

Table 1: UCP's Computational Dimensions' Derivation of the Four Physical Feature

<u>Framework/Consist.</u>	<u>Frame</u>	<u>Object</u>
<u>Consistent</u>	<u>"Space"</u>	<u>"Mass"</u>
<u>Inconsistent</u>	<u>"Energy"</u>	<u>"Time"</u>

"Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) – not only of the Four (basic) Physical Features, but also of GRT & QM (e.g., as "special-cased" within its UCF, as Einstein envisioned!) let us examine two derivatives of this singular UCF, i.e., of a Relativistic and Quantum Formats!

The UCF's Relativistic Format:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \left. \begin{array}{c} \text{E} * \text{s} \\ \text{t} \end{array} \right\} = \left. \begin{array}{c} \text{M} * \text{c}^2 \\ \text{h} \end{array} \right\}
 \end{array}$$

in which GRT's (famous) "Energy-Mass Equivalence" is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF's Quantum Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} \text{t} * \text{m} \\ \text{c}^2 \end{array} \right\} = \left. \begin{array}{c} \text{s} * \text{e} * \text{h} \\ \text{c}^2 \end{array} \right\}$$

in which "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" ("complimentary pairs") are embedded as "special cases" within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of "G-D'S PHYSICS").

Interestingly, this (latter) new "G-D's Physics" UCP's (∇) computation of the UCF's "Quantum Format" clearly reveals a much "deeper" understanding of the basic "computational constraint" imposed by Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" that stems from "G-D's Physics" singular higher-ordered UCP's simultaneous computation of those Four (basic) Physical Features (for all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe) – rather than as "caused" by any (direct) "material-causal" physical interac-

tion/s between any (two subatomic) "probe" and "target" elements; which serves as the current QM's "theoretical explanation" for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" (e.g., and associated assumed "collapse" of the "target's probability wave-function" – as "caused" by this direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the subatomic probe and target elements)!? This is because if we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" (novel) UCP's computational definitions of these Four basic Physical Features (above) – arising from the four possible combinations of the two Computational Dimensions: "Framework" ("frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent"): "Frame" – "consistent" (e.g., "space") or "inconsistent" (e.g., "energy"), and "Object" – "consistent" (e.g., "mass") or "inconsistent" ("time")! Then, we can immediately see that the real "intrinsic computational-complimentary" reason for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" is not any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between the subatomic "probe" and "target's" (assumed "probability wave function") elements! But rather, this "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity" is the real reason for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" stems from the "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity": i.e., since the UCP simultaneously computes both the "Framework" – "consistent" ("space") and "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") and "inconsistent" ("time") values of any given object (e.g., exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec'), therefore any increase in the accuracy level of the measurement of any one of these "UCP's computational pairs", i.e., "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") necessarily leads to a proportional decrease in the other "UCP's computational pair's" accuracy level!

Moreover, since this singular (higher-ordered) UCP simultaneously computes all Four Physical Features (for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s), therefore the singular "Universal Computational Formula" completely integrates (e.g., for the first time in Physics!) those Four Physical Features as "secondary computational by-products" of the same singular (higher-ordered) UCP computation! Indeed, as can be seen from the two (abovementioned) "Relativistic" and "Quantum" Formats of this singular UCF, we can see that "G-D's Physics" novel UCF completely integrates – not only between those Four basic Physical Features, but also completely integrates GRT & QM as "special cases" within this broader and (indeed) exhaustive new theoretical framework! Hence, not only do those key Relativistic "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ("E = Mc²") and Quantum's Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" (e.g., stemming not from any direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the subatomic "probe" and "target" elements, but is rather due to

the "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity"! being embedded within the singular UCF's Relativistic and Quantum Formats, but more broadly, its been previously shown that all key Relativistic and Quantum phenomena and laws are being replicated (and indeed "transcended" as merely representing "special cases" within "G-D's Physics" more exhaustive theoretical framework).

4. "G-D's Physics" UCF's Complete Unification of the Four Forces!

Indeed, as shown previously, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers an alternative theoretical explanation for all of Relativistic and Quantum phenomena – solely based on its newly discovered (abovementioned) "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), which simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" for all exhaustive spatial pixel/c comprising the entire physical universe (of each consecutive UF's frame/s) – as secondary computational by-products of the UCP's singular computation! This also means that the Four (basic) Forces of Nature – i.e., the Weak and Strong Forces, and the Electromagnetic Force, and the Gravitational Force are all solely derived (and produced) by this singular higher-ordered UCP's UCF description of the UCP's simultaneous computation of each of the universe's exhaustive spatial pixels four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – as "Frame's" or "Object's" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computations! This is where (we begin realizing)"G-d's Physic" (abovementioned) UCP's new Computational Definitions for each of these Four Physical Features – also necessarily gives rise- and (in fact) includes- the UCP's computation of the various forms of "energy", i.e., including those specific to each of these "three" Forces: the "Weak", "Strong" and "Electromagnetic" Forces;

"Energy"

$$E: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}\{UF(i)\} - \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}\{UF(n)\}) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

$$\text{such that: } f_{j\{x,y,z\}}\{UF(n)\} > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}\{UF's(i..n)\}$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

Likewise, the UCP's (abovementioned novel) Computational Definition of "Mass" – i.e., (as shown above) which gives rise to what appears as the "Gravitational Force", as manifesting through the UCP's (abovementioned) "Universal Computational Formula"!

"Mass"

$$M: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}\{UF's(i)\} - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}\{UF's(i..n)\}] \leq n * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

As noted above (and previously), the UCP's computation of any type of "energy" is computed by this singular higher-ordered UCP as the degree of "displacement" of any (relativistic or quantum) object relative the coordinates of the entire Universal Frame/s across a series of UF's frames; this means that the "root" for all three "Strong, Weak and Electromagnetic Forces is derived from the UCP's computation of their degree of "displacement" across a given series of UF's frames! Moreover, based on the complete integration of those four basic physical features comprising any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe through the UCP's Universal Computational Formula (UCF), therefore the entire array of subatomic particles described by the Standard Model – amongst which those Three Nuclear Forces operate are exhaustively described by the UCP's UCF! Indeed, the multifarious different levels of electromagnetic charge, mass, en-

ergy values etc. of each of these particular Standard Model particles and components manifests as one of the specific configurations- and relationships- described by the UCP's newly discovered UCF! In other words, the Three Strong, Weak, Electromagnetic Forces describe different levels and configurations of the UCP's singular higher-ordered UCP's computation of the degree of any given particle (object) "displacement" across a given series of UF's frames! In that sense, there is no real "difference" between the UCP's computation of the degree of "displacement" of the Strong, Weak or Electromagnetic Forces operating within the nucleus or between the nucleus and its surrounding particles or between particles and other elements; In fact, the whole theoretical conceptualization of the very computational definitions of each of these multifarious Standard Model particles – including their "mass", "energy", "localization" and "temporal" values is viewed (for the first time) as one singular fully integrated computation by the UCP, rather than existing as "separate" and "independent" particles operating by different (Three) Strong, Weak or Electromagnetic Forces...

No longer are the various Standard Model particles viewed as "independent" entities, nor do the Three Forces operating between them or uniting them seem as "separate" or "independent"; rather, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm's discovery of the singular higher ordered "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) completely unifies all of these apparently different subatomic particles and the Three Forces governing them as manifestations of different possible relationships described by this singular higher-ordered UCP UCF! Indeed, it is suggested that just as the discovery of the "Periodic Table" provided a "blue-print" for the basic constitution of all possible chemical elements in Nature, just as Watson, & Crick discovery of the basic constituent elements of the DNA gave Science its basic understanding of the basic "building-blocks" of all Genetic-Biological organisms (and functions); so does "G-d's Physics" 21st Century Physics Paradigm's discovery of the new "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) provides Theoretical Physics (and Science more generally) the basic understanding of all of Nature's basic (possible) "plethora" of subatomic particles and Four basic Forces, i.e., the Strong & Weak Forces, the Electromagnetic Force and the Gravitational Force! It is suggested that by using this newly discovered UCF we can find and identify all of the known "Standard Model" particles – and potentially additional "prospective!" (i.e., yet to be discovered!) e.g., based upon the precise interrelationships between any given particle's "mass", "energy", "spatial" and "temporal" values (see below)! Hence, this new UCF also integrates and unifies between the Three (Strong, Weak and Electromagnetic) Nuclear Forces (of the Standard Model and Quantum Mechanics) and the Gravitational Force (of General Relativity Theory) – simply because the Gravitational Force, alike these other Three Forces is computed by the singular higher-ordered UCF! As noted above, "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm offers a completely new and different theoretical account for General Relativity's "Gravitational Force", as well as for the Three Nuclear Forces, e.g., as stemming from the UCP's UCF computation of the four integrated and complimentary physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – not as being "caused" by certain "massive objects" "curving "Space-Time", but rather as being produced by the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe; Specifically, what "appears" as General Relativity's "Gravitational Force" is the result of the UCP's computation of certain "regions" of each consecutive UF's frame/s to be comprised of "High-Mass; Low Energy" (HMLE) regions which are therefore computed as "spatially-consistent" regions which remain relatively "constant" across a given series of UF's frames, as opposed to other regions constituting these series of UF's frames which may be defined as constituting "Low-Mass; High Energy" ("LMHE") regions which therefore do not appear as "spatially-consistent" across a series of UF's frames! This differential UCP's computation of those HMLE vs. LMHE regions (according to "G-d's Physics" New Computational Definition of "Mass") creates an appearance of the "curvature" of "Space-Time" around certain "massive objects"?!

In much the same manner, "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm also offers an

alternative new theoretical account for these "Three Forces" – not as being "caused" by any direct (or indirect) physical interactions between any of the "Standard Model" list of existing particles; but rather as being produced by the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), thereby producing those "apparent" subatomic particle's associated "Three Forces"! It is perhaps important to highlight the unique new (expansive, higher-ordered) perspective offered by "G-D's Physics" New 21st Century Paradigm – shedding a complete new light upon the complete unification of the Four basic Forces based on the operation of the singular, higher-ordered UCP; First (as we've already seen), due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s, and the discovery of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Paradigm– then this "G-D's Physics" (novel) ACC Scientific Paradigm (principally) negates the very possibility of the existence of any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frames! This implies that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any of the subatomic elementary particles that are currently assumed to "transfer" the effects of Three (out of four) Forces – the Weak, Strong and Electromagnetic! As noted previously, this principle negation of the existence of any direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two or more particle/s (or exhaustive spatial pixels) is most apparent when we take into consideration the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe (e.g., and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels and subatomic particles) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s – which negates the very possibility of the existence of any such physical interactions or effects transferred across any two consecutive or non-consecutive UF's frames! Hence, the basic "material-causal" assumption underlying Relativity's explanation of the curvature of Space-Time as "caused" by its direct physical interaction with certain "massive objects" (as evinced in Einstein's Equations), as well as underlying the current "material-causal" Quantum, Standard Model explanation of the other (three) Forces – Strong, Weak and Electromagnetic as being "carried by" certain elementary particles being transferred between particles is strictly negated by the New "G-d's Physics A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! Instead, based on "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's discovery (and description) of the manner in which the singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) – e.g., through the UCP's "Universal Computational Formula" (and based on the UCP's new computational definitions of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" associated with two of its Computational Dimensions) offers an entirely new (and fascinating) way of viewing each of these Four Forces as arising from si-

multaneous and integrated computation of this singular higher-ordered UCP! In other words, the manner in which "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm unifies between the "Three Forces" and the "Gravitational Force" is based on its discovery of the singular higher-ordered UCP's simultaneous computation of all of the physical universe's exhaustive spatial pixels based on its unitary "Universal Computational Formula" (UCP) which completely unified between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time"; According to this New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm theoretical framework, both the "Gravitational Force" and the "Three (other) Forces" represent "apparent, phenomenal and transient Forces" which are computed together by the UCP's UCF for each of the universe's consecutive UF's frames!

Indeed, from a theoretical standpoint, "G-D's Physics" (proven) capacity to fully integrate between GRT & QM (as well as between the Four basic Physical Features & also between the Four Forces!) can be glanced from:

A) "G-D's Physics" Computational Perspective: SST, MST & EST Computations!

B) "G-D's Physics" Applied Physics Perspective:

a. "The UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table"!

b. Call for "G-D's Physics" Prospective Empirical Validations:

i. UNCIARE-JRH Precise & Longitudinal Measurements!

ii. Differential Mass-Related UF's Accelerators' Measurements!

3-A) "G-D's Physics" Computational Perspective: SST, MST & EST Computations

Indeed, "G-D's Physics" resolution of the apparent "Relativistic-Quantum Inconsistency" may be viewed based on its singular (higher-ordered) UCP's ("simultaneous") computation of "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST), "Multiple Spatial-Temporal" (MST) and "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" (EST) types of computation, giving rise to increasingly more "exhaustive" forms of computation that integrate (and indeed resolve) this apparent "Relativistic-Quantum Inconsistency". According to this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation- and "resolution"- of this apparent "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from the UCP's simultaneous (singular higher-ordered) computation of all "Single Spatial-Temporal" computation ("SST"): subatomic "particle" or "relativistic object" – i.e., relating to only "one" spatial-temporal point, at any given moment; "Multi Spatial-Temporal" computation (MST): (subatomic) "wave" – i.e., relating to at least "two" points being measured at any point in time; or "Exhaustive Spatial Temporal" (EST) computation – i.e., relating to all "exhaustive" spatial pixels comprising an entire "Universal Frame"! (Table 2);

Table 2: UCP'S "SST", "MST" & "EST" Computations!

UCP's Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. "ST" Points	1	2+	All Points

The manner in which "G-D's Physics" new theoretical conceptualization conceives of the UCP's computation of those Four basic Physical Features, as well as of its simultaneous computation of SST, MST and EST values – allows for a complete integration of Relativistic and Quantum Models, based on the discovery of the UCP's singular "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), as shown above:

The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...x} [Px] (a...z) t * m

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

Wherein the UCP represented by the Hebrew Letter "ח" computes at an extremely rapid rate, e.g., of "c2/h" = 1.36-50 (sec') simultaneously every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising every consecutive UF's – including the UCP's complete integration of those Four basic Physical Features through the UCF's: s * e / t * m computation (e.g., for each exhaustive spatial pixel – from "a to z")!

3-B) "G-D's Physics" Applied Physics Perspective:

a. "The UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table"!

Another important facet of "G-D's Physics" complete integration of both GRT & QM – as "special cases" within the broader theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) can be glanced from "G-D's Physics" "Critical Prediction" of the existence of a ("prospective") "The UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table", which will be derived from the different possible computational relationships for each of the "known" Standard Model's subatomic particles, as well as the expected discovery of multiple prospective subatomic particles that can be derived from the specific stipulated computational relationships between the UCF's Four basic Physical Features, e.g., and their associated (abovementioned) Computational Definitions;

The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...x} [Px] (a...z) t * m

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

"Energy"

$$E: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i...n)]$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's. In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes): $M: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$ where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

"Mass"

$$M: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - [O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i...n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"Time"

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i...n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i...n)\} \text{ such that: } T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - [O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i...n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Specifically, it is predicted that every existent (e.g., already discovered) or "prospective" (e.g., to be discovered) subatomic particle would conform to the UCF's stipulated computational relationships between the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – alongside the above outlined computational definitions of each of these four physical features! In this manner, this novel major discovery made by "G-d's Physics" New "UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table" may be (somewhat) likened to the "historic discovery" of the Chemical "Periodic-Table" which explicated the mutual basis- and atomic values constraints- imposed based on the realization that the difference between the various elements (e.g., also pertaining to the then known chemical elements, as well as to the then "unknown prospective" elements that were verified based on this stipulated "Periodic-Table", subsequently); This is because "G-d's Physics" discovery of this novel "UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table" also reveals the basic underlying UCP's computational "mechanism" and "constraints" for all (already discovered and "prospective" (to be discovered) elementary particles, i.e., as constrained by the UCP's UCF's basic stipulated relationships between the four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"), and

their accompanying UCP's computational definitions!

Indeed, to the extent that prospective validations of this "G-D's Physics" Predicted **"UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table"** will be empirically validated (i.e., of even a single "existent" or "prospective" subatomic particle) which conforms to the UCF's computational relationships between the Four basic Physical Features, then this will unequivocally support "G-D's Physics" as being capable of offering an alternative computational approach to the Standard Model – i.e., which replicates all of the Standard Model's known particle's physical properties, but offers a higher-ordered broader (and exhaustive) novel "A-Causal Computational" (ACC) theoretical framework describing QM's Standard Model as a "special-case" within "G-D's Physics" UCF (e.g., that fully integrates both GRT & QM as integral parts of this singular higher-ordered UCF)!

3-B-b) Call for "G-D's Physics" Prospective Empirical Validations:

i. "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Precise & Longitudinal Measurements!

Based upon "G-D's Physics" discovery of that singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) of the entire physical universe (e.g., at every "minimal time-point" at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!") Another (novel) Theoretical Postulate of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) which stipulates that whenever there exists a large group of individual human-beings such as during the two days of the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (JRH) in which Millions of Jews (all around the world) focus on the singularity of this "UCP", then this brings about an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) – which can explain the (otherwise) "unexplained" gap that exists between the early Cosmological value of the universe's rate of expansion and the current (significantly increased) Astronomical rate of the universe's expansion, i.e., recently termed: the "Hubble's Tension"!

Hence, "G-D's Physics" alternative theoretical explanation for the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion is given through G-D's Physics "Uni-

verse's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Expansion" (UNCIARE), e.g., brought about by a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), such as during the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah's" (JRH) two days special time-interval in which Millions of Jews (all over the world) focus upon this singular (higher-ordered) UCP! Hence, the accelerated expansion of the universe's expansion rate is brought about by the JRH-CHCF, which results in a predicted "UNCIARE-JRH" annual increase in the universe's expansion rate! (e.g., rather than is the result of the "purely hypothetical" "Dark-Matter" [DM] concept – i.e., which is in fact negated by G-D'S Physics' NSP: a) because this purely hypothetical DM concept failed to be verified experimentally for the past two full decades?! And b) due to "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Computational Duality Principle" [CDP] which principally negates its existence, based on a computational-empirical analysis! see below). This UNCIARE-JRH annual increase in the universe's expansion rate has been calculated to comprise a **"*Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ per year**; This (novel) G-D's Physics unique "Critical Prediction" of the UNCIARE-JRH's increase of an MAI (e.g., annually) opens an entirely new "window of opportunity" for the validation of the G-D'S Physics NSP – as more valid than the Old MCR Paradigm (e.g., of GRT & QM), i.e., both through: a) "Precise" MAI (sensitive) annual Astronomical measurements "during" the JRH's two days' special time-interval; B) Based on "Longitudinal" Astronomical/Cosmological measurements indicating a "cumulative" increase in the universe's expansion rate over any given "time-interval" (e.g., such as over the past 10, 50 or 100 years, or potentially much longer time-intervals, etc., as delineated below)!

Specifically, the significant increase in the universe's measured rate of expansion, i.e., from its (initial) Cosmological "Background Radiation" rate to its (current) "Astronomical" (significantly higher) rate of expansion – termed" the "Hubble's Tension"³¹⁻³⁹; precisely supports G-D's Physics' assumed "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE-JRH) "Critical Prediction", as more valid than the Old MCR's (GRT's) "constant-expansion rate" corresponding prediction (see Figure 3):

This is because, according to Old MCR's Paradigm's GRT "Big-Bang" Model, the universe's expansion rate should be "constant" – as caused by the assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event (e.g., and two additional "Exceptional Expansive Events" (or factors, EEE's; as delineated below and previously). Specifically, the (purely hypothetical) "Dark Matter" [DM] concept, which is assumed by the Old MCR Paradigm to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe (e.g., but which could not be detected experimentally for the past two decades despite numerous attempts to do so!?) – could only account for such a "constant rate" of the universe's expansion, because the quantity of this purely hypothetical DM is (itself) "constant" (e.g., or may in fact "diminish" over time, hence leading to a deceleration of the universe's expansion rate...) Hence, according to the Old MCR's GRT Model of the universe, the universe has been created 13.8 Billion years ago, and since then its expansion rate should have been "constant" (i.e., as further delineated below through this MCR's assumed three purely hypothetical EEE's). In contrast, according to the G-D's Physics (novel) Scientific Paradigm, there exists a "Universe's non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE), which is brought about through the JRH's (two days) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) upon the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which increases the universe's rate of expansion by a Minute Annual Increase (MAI) (i.e., of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ (during the JRH's two days' time-interval!)) Hence, the existence of this (specific JRH associated) CHCF is seen as "critical" for the continuous (cumulative) increase in the universe's "accelerated" expansion rate, which also points at the G-D's Physics "Six Days Creation Model" (delineated previously) highlighting the centrality of this CHCF as a key (essential and necessary) factor for the empirically observed "UNCIARE" (e.g., otherwise "unexplained") increase in the universe's expansion rate! Consequently, the G-D'S PHYSICS introduces an entirely different account of the universe's (stipulated) age (and "origin") of the physical universe, e.g., to be derived from the MAI's predicted (annual increase) in the universe's expansion rate: originated 5785 years ago!

Therefore, the current article provides initial (unequivocal) empirical support for the G-D's Physics UNCIARE's (unique) "Critical Prediction" regarding the (cumulative) MAI's increase in the universe's expansion rate – i.e., producing the otherwise ("unexplained") "Hubble's Tension"! This is (once again) because unlike GRT's "Big-Bang" Model which assumes a "constant" rate of the universe's expansion (e.g., and the universe's creation based on an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event dated 13.8 Billion years ago) – leading to an "unexplained" "Hubble's Tension" Enigma which cannot account for a significant increase in the universe's expansion rate over time; the (novel) G-D'S PHYSICS explains the universe's (continuous) "origination" by that (singular, higher-ordered) UCP, based on its continuous computation- "dissolution" "re-computation" and "evolution"- of every exhaustive spatial pixel (e.g., simultaneously), at an incredible rate of " c^2/h " = $1.36^{-50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$! thereby leading to the UCP's production of an incredibly rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every such "minimal time-point"! Indeed, according to this (entirely new) conception of the universe's (constant and continuous) "origination"- "dissolution"- "re-computation"- and "development"- by this singular (higher-ordered) UCP; and the (abovementioned) centrality of the human CHCF (e.g., during the JRH's two days' special time-interval), which brings about an annual "MAI" increase in the UCP's rate of the universe's expansion rate – leads to the G-D's Physics (clear and unique) "Critical Prediction" of "UNCIARE", which is empirically validated- by the (otherwise "unexplained" by the Old MCR's GRT "Big-Bang Model)! Indeed, it is due to the G-D's Physics centrality of the JRH (two days) CHCF (time-interval) – and specifically the MAI's (cumulative) increase in the universe's expansion rate (over time), that the G-D's Physics stipulated age of the physical universe is only 5785 (rather than the Big-Bang Model's stipulated 13.8 Billion years!

In order to further support this (novel) G-D's Physics UCP's CHCF (JRH's) model of the universe's UNCIARE increase (over time), we highlight its (conceptual computational) negation of the Old MCR's Big-Bang Model of a "constantly" expanding universe: According to the Old MCR Paradigm's GRT "Big-Bang" Model, the universe's current rate of expansion can be explained based on three "Exceptional Expansive Events" (or factors, EEE's): 1) Initial "Big-Bang" Event: the creation of the entire physical universe based on an initial nuclear event. 2) Cosmological Factor: exceptional ("unexplained") anti-gravitational effect that is causing the universe's constant-rate increase in its expansion rate. 3) Purely hypothetical ("unexplained") "Dark-Matter" Concept: that is assumed (somehow) to "cause" an increase in the universe's expansion!?! However, even beyond the (perplexing) failure of Astronomers to experimentally detect the actual existence of this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept (for the past twenty years!?) even from a theoretical standpoint, this (purely hypothetical) Dark Matter (DM) concept – could not account for an increase in the universe's expansion rate!?! This is because even if there existed such a (purely hypothetical) DM concept (or element) – assumed to (somehow) "push" the outer-galactic elements in the universe, it could only do so at a "constant-rate", e.g., because it's quantity cannot increase over time! This means that over time, the rate of the universe's expansion could only remain constant – or (much more likely) decrease!

In fact, the very (computational) structure of GRT's (three) "Exceptional Expansive Effects" (EEE's), e.g., (1) "Big-Bang" event; (2) "Cosmological Factor"; (3) "Dark-Matter" – all share two (very important) characteristics: a) These three EEE's are based on the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm's basic "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) structure; which has been shown by the G-D's Physics "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) to be "computationally flawed", i.e., lead to an inevitable "logical-inconsistency" and (ensuing) "computationally-indefiniteness", and are therefore negated by the CDP (as "invalid")! b) These three EEE's can only account for a "constant rate" of the universe's expansion (e.g., or more likely a "decreasing rate" of the universe's expansion) "over time" – but cannot account for an "increased rate" of the universe's expansion over time!?

Indeed, when we examine each of these three EEE's (e.g., individually), we can see that none of them can account for an "increasing rate" of the universe's expansion: a) The "Big-Bang" (initial) nuclear event cannot account for an increasing rate of the universe's expansion, since the initial "impetus" of the Big-Bang's nuclear explosion necessarily pushes the universe's outer galactic elements at a certain "constant" rate, (e.g., or more likely will decrease over time) but will not "increase" over time! b) The "Cosmological Constant" – despite it being "unexplainable": e.g., there is no "etiological" physical explanation for its repulsive effect, or the nature of such an effect; in any event such an "axiomatic repulsive effect" must also be "constant"! This is due to the fact that this "Cosmological Constant" has been defined as "constant"! c) "Dark-Matter" (DM): this purely hypothetical DM – despite the fact that it could not be detected experimentally (for the past twenty years, despite numerous attempts to do so!?) could only "push" those outer galactic regions in a "constant" (e.g., or more likely a "decreasing" rate) over time; this i.e., because, once again, unless this "DM" could somehow "increase in quantity" (over time), its effect could not "increase" over time!

Indeed, an examination of the SRCS Computational Structure of each of these three EEE's has revealed that they all share the same basic SRCS' (intrinsic) "computational flaw", which is exposed through the CDP – and points at the inevitable existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP), which according to the G-D'S PHYSICS (simultaneously) computes all exhaustive spatial points in the universe Paradigm at the "unfathomable" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50} \text{ (sec)}^{-1}$!

The "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) Negation of the GRT's SRNCS Structure!

According to G-D's Physics' "Computational Duality Principle" Postulate, the basic "Computational Structure" of GRT's Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., termed: a "Self-Referential Negative Computational System" (SRNCS) is "computationally flawed", i.e., it inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" – which are contradicted by GRT's Computational System's proven empirical capacity to determine the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion, thereby pointing at the singular higher-ordered UCP that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe! Specifically, the GRT's SRNCS Computational Structure assumes that it is solely based on the direct physical interactions (di) between GRT's basic "Curved Space-Time" (due to the presence of certain "massive-objects") "Contractive-Stable Universe" [C-STMo : CSU], e.g., describing a universe that is fundamentally "contracting" or being "stable" (i.e., "constant"); and the three (abovementioned) EEE's "expulsive-effects", e.g.: BB, CC, and DE – all describing a (constant) "accelerated-expansion" of the universe produces such a SRNCS Computational Structure:

GRT's SRNCS:

PR{[C-STMo : CSU], [EEE-BB, CC, DE/DM]} → "Not C-STMo : CSU" / di ?!

Wherein it is assumed that GRT's fundamentally assumed "Contractive-Stable Universe" (e.g., due to the curvature of Space-Time by certain "massive objects") : [C-STMo : CSU] seems to both "exist" and "Not exist" at the same "di" computational level, e.g., constituting a basic "logical-inconsistency" and associated "computational indeterminacy" implying an (apparent) inability of such a SRNCS System to determine the "existence" or "non-existence" of this {[C-STMo : CSU]}? But, since empirically the universe is in fact expanding (at an accelerated rate!), e.g., "Not {[C-STMo : CSU]}"; therefore, according to the CDP there must exist a singular higher-ordered UCP that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each UF's at the rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec⁻¹)!

Announcement of G-D's Physics Call for Astronomers to Validate the UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction Through Precise & Longitudinal Measurements!"

A call is made to all leading Astronomers, Cosmologists and Universities to collaborate with Dr. Bentovich (e.g., directly through his personal email: drbentwich@gmail.com) in validating two additional (prospective unique) "Critical Predictions" comprising:

A. Precise Astronomical Measurement of the UNCIARE-JRH's Critical Prediction: of an increase in the current Astronomical Value of the Universe's Expansion Rate, i.e., by a "*Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc that occurred during the last JRH: on Oct. 3rd -4th, 2024 (e.g., relative to the measured rate of the universe's expansion prior to Oct. 3- 4th 2024; with this increased MAI value carrying over through the whole next JRH – until the next JRH scheduled for Sep. 22nd& 23rd, 2025); "G-D's Physics" therefore also predicted a further (singular) MAI increase in the rate of the universe's expansion beginning from these two (prospective) days of the past JRH (Sep. 22nd& 23rd, 2025) of another 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc increase in the universe's expansion rate (e.g., that will carry through the whole next JRH)!

B. Longitudinal measurement of the (same) UNCIARE-JRH's cumulative MAI's – across any given time-span! Thus, for instance, this second manner of testing (and validating) the G-D's Physics UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction could be experimentally tested at particularly set "time-points", e.g., for instance: a) Before 10 years (e.g., 2014 after the JRH of 2014): a predicted 10 * MAI = 10 *MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc "decrease" from

the current Hubble's constant, i.e., ; b) Before 50 years (e.g., (e.g., 2014 after the JRH of 2014): a predicted 10 X MAI = 50 * MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc decrease from the current Hubble's constant, c) Before 100 years : a predicted 100 X MAI = MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc decrease from the current Hubble's constant.

iii. "G-D's Physics Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances"

Based on the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" (unique) "Critical Prediction" regarding the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated findings, indicating that the UCP's differential computation of the "Mass" value/s of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle than the (equivalent negatively charged) electron particle – led to the Muon's associated "altered Muon Hydrogen Proton's" measurements as more "spatially-consistent" (e.g., according to "G-D's Physics'" new UCP's Computational Definitions of "Mass") than the equivalent "Standard Hydrogen Proton" (see above Results); therefore an even more direct empirical measurement of "G-D's Physics" "Differential Mass UF's Appearances" **Critical Prediction** regards a comparison of an Accelerator's precise measurements of the significantly greater number of times that such a ("more massive") Muon particle would appear across a given series of UF's frames (i.e., or in fact a certain measurable sample thereof!) than the "less-massive" electron particle!

Therefore, it may be said that these "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings lay the (theoretical) foundations for the prospective "G-D's Physics Differential-Mass UF's Appearances" Critical Prediction; because they indicate that the "more massive" Muon particle is measured as "spatially more consistent" than the (relatively) "less massive" particle, i.e., both in its "proton-radius size" and its "spatial measurement accuracy"! Indeed, the aim of this (prospective) "G-D's Physics Differential-Mass UF's Appearances" (unique) "Critical Prediction" is to test "G-D's Physics'" (novel) conception of "Mass" as representing the UCP's computation of an "Object-consistent" measure":

"Mass"

M: [Oi{x,y,z}UF's(i)] – On{x,y,z}UF's(i...n)] ≤ n * h [{UF's (i...n)]

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

Specifically, the aim of this article is to test a direct (prospective) "G-D's Physics Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances"(unique) "Critical Prediction": predicting that the (relatively) "more-massive" Muon particle would appear across a greater number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM) than the "less-massive" electron particle: Contrasting between the number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM, e.g., see below their mathematical calculation) in which a 'more massive particle' (i.e., the Muon), would be detected relative to a "less-massive" particle (i.e., the electron); It is suggested that in order to test "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances"(unique)it is necessary to contrast the number of FTM in which the 'more-massive' 'Muon' relative appears, relative to the number of FTM in which the 'less-massive' electron particle would be detected; However, a key point to be noted is that the "temporal resolution" of most Accelerators is far less "sensitive" than the hypothesized rate at which the Universal Computational Principle (UCP) computes the series of USCF's frames, i.e., "c²/h"=1.45⁻⁴² sec⁻¹ – with certain Accelerators reaching almost the speed of light "c = 3.33-6 sec⁻¹" (e.g., regarded as the 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' accuracy level in this experiment), producing a magnitude difference of x-36 sec⁻¹; Nevertheless, it is suggested that even if we opt to "sample"the FTM's at such a "decreased" temporal resolution (below) the speed of light "c = 3.33-6 sec⁻¹, i.e., in effect sampling a significantly de-

creased temporal accuracy level [e.g., x-36 sec' decreased magnitude of accuracy relative to the rate at which the Universal Computational Principle (UCP) computes the series of USCF's frames (i.e., " $c^2/h=1.45^{-42}$ sec')]; we can still expect that the "more massive" Muon particle would appear at a greater percentage of these " $c = 3.33\text{-}6$ sec' FTM's samplings relative to the number of (the same decreased accuracy) FTM's samplings in which the electron would be detected!

As stated above, in calculating "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances"(unique) "Critical Prediction", e.g., regarding the significantly smaller number of FTM's in which the 'electron' particle would be detected relative to the number of (such) FTM's in which the 'Muon' may be measured, we need to correct for the known subatomic (quantum theory related) bias towards a slightly "easier" measurement of such 'more-massive' 'Muon' particle relative to the measurements of a 'less massive' 'electron' particle; In other words "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances""Critical Prediction" regarding the significantly greater FTM's at which the 'more massive' Muon particle(M) would be detected, relative to the number of (equivalent) FTM's at which the 'less-massive' electron (e) particle would be detected should subtract the "quantum measurement bias" (QMB) towards a more 'sensitive temporal measurement' of more massive particle:

FTM(M) – QMB >FTM(e)

Nevertheless, the called for precision and longitudinal measurements of the G-D's Physics UNCIARE-JRH will provide an even more accurate ascertainment of the G-D's Physics "Six-Day Creation Model" (SDCM) and its associated (key) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) as central to the origination- development- and (in fact) "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" State of the entire physical universe! This is because to the extent that these (more specific) Precision & Longitudinal Measurements of the UNCIARE-JRH Critical Predictions will be validated empirically, then this will (unequivocally) support the New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm, indicating that the origination- sustenance- and development- of the entire physical universe is totally dependent upon that singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ (sec)!" Moreover, according to this New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm the whole origination-sustenance- dynamics- and development- of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP to develop from an initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards attaining a Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity in which Science (and the whole of Humanity) will recognize this singularity of the UCP, and its characterization by such "intrinsic-sublime" properties as: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will therefore also characterize the existence and behavior of the whole of Humanity! Therefore, the current (truly) "historic-pivotal turning point" associated with the direct empirical validation of the G-D'S PHYSICS as more valid than both GRT & QM (e.g., and in fact completely unifying between them, as well as for the first time in Physics between the Four basic Physical Features: of "time", "space", "energy" and "mass", as well as between the Four basic Forces!) is not "limited" only to the sphere of Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics, or even Science (more generally), but in fact represents a Major Turning Point (and even "Apex") in the whole development of Humanity and the entire physical universe, i.e., since it points at the "fulfillment" of the UCP's "pre-planned" "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the entire physical universe, in which the whole of Humanity (finally) recognizes) this singular higher-ordered UCP, and lives accordingly in complete Peace & Harmony!

Hence, it may be appropriate to end this (significant) article with Mai-

monides' ("prophetic") description of the state of Humanity during this (predicted) "Perfected Geulah State":

Intriguingly then, "G-D'S PHYSICS" points at Humanity's (current) entering of the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" is extremely reminiscent of the Isaiah's (well-known) Prophecy: And they shall beat their swords into plowshares, and their spears into pruning hooks; nation shall not lift up sword against nation, neither shall they learn war anymore... (Isaiah 2:4) And the Great Maimonides' prophecy regarding "That time (of Geulah) there will be no hunger or war, jealousy or competition... and the whole World's preoccupation will be only to know "G-D"! (Hilchut Melachim, 12:3-5)

Dedication

This article is dedicated to the Alter Rabbi (Rabbi Shneur Zalman) on his passing (Yurzeit) 23rd of Tevet, and to the Lubavitcher Rabbi (as well as to the Great Maimonides and all other Heads of Israel, Chassidic Rabbis) for their unwavering striving and efforts to uplift the Jewish People and Humanity as a whole towards that Perfected "Geulah" State in which Humanity (and Science) will realize the singularity of "G-D" Reality underlying and transcending the physical universe and realizing that "Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity in which all human-beings will regard each other as integral parts of this singular higher-ordered "G-D" Reality, therefore leading a Peaceful, Harmonious, Good existence (and behavior). It is also dedicated to my Beloved (diseased) Mother Dr. Tirzah Bentwich (Bat Yitzchak). This article is dedicated to the full & fast recovery of RabbiDovHacohen Ben Shoshana (G-D willing).

References

1. Bentwich, J. (2012a) "Harmonizing Quantum Mechanics and Relativity Theory". Theoretical Concepts of Quantum Mechanics, Intech (ISBN 979-953-307-377-3), Chapter 22: 515-550.
2. Bentwich, J. (2012b) "Theoretical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory". Theoretical Concepts of Quantum Mechanics, (ISBN 979-953-307-3773), Chapter 23: 551-598.
3. Bentwich, J. (2013b). "The Theoretical Ramifications of the Computational Unified Field Theory". Advances in Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-1089-7), Chapter 28: 671-882.
4. Bentwich, J. (2013c). The Computational Unified Field Theory (G-D'S PHYSICS): A Candidate Theory of Everything. Advances in Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-1089-7) Chapter 18: 395-436.
5. Bentwich, J. (2015). The Computational Unified Field Theory (G-D'S PHYSICS): A Candidate 'Theory of Everything'. Selected Topics in Application of Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-2126-8) Chapter 6.
6. Bentwich, J. (2015). On the Geometry of Space, Time, Energy, and Mass: Empirical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory. Unified Field Mechanics: Natural Science Beyond the Veil of Spacetime (Proceedings of VIGIER IX Conference, Morgan State University, USA, 16-19 November 2014).
7. Bentwich, J. (2016) The 'Computational Unified Field Theory': A Paradigmatic Shift. Research & Reviews: Journal of Pure & Applied Physics.
8. Bentwich, J. (2017a) The Computational Unified Field Theory: Could 'Dark Matter' & 'Dark Energy' be "Superfluous"? SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
9. Bentwich, J. (2017b) The Computational Unified Field Theory: Explaining the Universe from "Without". SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
10. Bentwich, J. (2019d).The 'Computational Unified Field Theory' (G-D'S PHYSICS): Redefining Mass, Gravity & the Physical Universe. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19 (6), Special Issue.
11. Bentwich, J. (2019d).Astronomical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory (G-D'S PHYSICS) "Critical Prediction" &

- Resolution of the "Universe's Accelerated Expansion Rate Enigma" (UAERE). The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19 (6), Special Issue.
12. Bentwich, J. (2019e) Urgent Call for Empirical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory's (G-D'S PHYSICS) New 21st Century 'A-Causal Computation' (ACC) Paradigm. Acta Scientific Applied Physics, Volume 1(1).
 13. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2020b). An Urgent Need for "G-D'S PHYSICS" New 21st Century Paradigm's Empirical Validation. Advances in Theoretical & Computational Physics. Volume 3: 59-65.
 14. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021). "G-D'S PHYSICS: A New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century. iUniverse. ISBN 9781532090370.
 15. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021b). "G-D'S PHYSICS": From Arbitrary Physical & Biological "Evolution" Towards A Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) Directed Morally-Perfected ("Geulah") Universe! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-D'S PHYSICS New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 16. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021c). "G-D'S PHYSICS": On the True Nature of "Dark-Energy" & "Dark-Matter". In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-D'S PHYSICS New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 17. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021d). The New "G-D'S PHYSICS" New Twenty-First Century Paradigm: A Morally Perfected ("Geulah") Directed New Physical Universe! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-D'S PHYSICS New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 18. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021g). "G-D'S PHYSICS" New 21st Century Paradigm: A Complete Integration of "Space" & "Energy", "Mass" & "Time"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-D'S PHYSICS New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 19. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021h). "G-D'S PHYSICS": Complete Unification of the Four Basic Forces of Nature & "Geulah"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-D'S PHYSICS New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
 20. Dahia, F.; Lemos, A.S. (2016). "Is the proton radius puzzle evidence of extra dimensions?". European Physical Journal. 76: 435. arXiv:1509.08735. Bibcode:2016EPJC...76..435D. doi:10.1140/epjc/s10052-016-4266-7. S2CID 118672005
 21. Karr, J.; Hilico, L. (2012). "Why three-body physics does not solve the proton-radius puzzle". Physical Review Letters. 109: 103401. arXiv:1205.0633. Bibcode:2012PhRvL.109j3401K. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.109.103401. PMID 23005286. S2CID 12752418
 22. Kuhn, Thomas S. (1962). The Structure of Scientific Revolutions (1st ed.). University of Chicago Press. pp. 172. LCCN 62019621
 23. Lestone, J.P. (4 October 2017). Muonic atom Lamb shift via simple means (Report). Los Alamos Report. Los Alamos National Laboratory. LA-UR-17-29148.
 24. Liu Y, McKeen D, Miller GA (2016). "Electroponic Scalar Boson and Muonic Puzzles". Physical Review Letters. 117: 101801. arXiv:1605.04612. Bibcode:2016PhRvL.117j1801L. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.117.101801. PMID 27636468. S2CID 20961
 25. Onofrio, R. (2013). "Proton radius puzzle and quantum gravity at the Fermi scale". EPL. 104: 20002. arXiv:1312.3469. Bibcode:2013EL....10420002O. doi:10.1209/0295-5075/104/20002. S2CID 119243594
 26. Planck Collaboration, Aghanim, N., Akrami, Y., et al. 2020, A&A, 641, A6.
 27. Pohl R, Antognini A, Nez F, Amaro FD, Biraben F, et al. (July 2010). "The size of the proton" (PDF). Nature. 466: 213–216. Bibcode:2010Natur.466..213P. doi:10.1038/nature09250. PMID 20613837. S2CID 4424731.
 28. Pohl R, et al. (2016a). "Laser spectroscopy of muonic deuterium". Science. 353: 669–673. Bibcode:2016Sci...353..669P. doi:10.1126/science.aaf2468. hdl:10316/80061. PMID 27516595. S2CID 206647315.
 29. Pohl R, et al. (16 September 2016b) "Proton-radius puzzle deepens". CERN Courier. After our first study came out in 2010, I was afraid some veteran physicist would get in touch with us and point out our great blunder. But the years have passed, and so far nothing of the kind has happened.
 30. Zyga, Lisa (November 26, 2013). "Proton radius puzzle may be solved by quantum gravity". Phys.org. Retrieved September 2, 2016.
 31. Riess A. G., Casertano S., Yuan W. et al (2018a). Is there any measurable redshift dependence on the SN Ia absolute magnitude? ApJ 861 126 33.
 32. Riess, A. G., Yuan, W., Macri, L. M., et al. (2022) ApJL, 934, L7.
 33. Riess, A.G., Gagandeep, S.A., Wenlong, Yuan W., .S., Casertano, S., Dolphin, A., Macri M., Breuval, L., Scolnic, D., Perrin, M., & Anderson R.I. (2024). ApJL 962 L17.
 34. Shajib A. J., Birrer S., Treu T. et al (2020). STRIDES: a 3.9 per cent measurement of the Hubble constant from the strong lens system DES J0408-5354. MNRAS 494 6072 34.
 35. Scolnic D., Rest A., Riess A. et al (2014). Systematic Uncertainties Associated with the Cosmological Analysis of the First PAN-STARRS1 Type Ia Supernova Sample. ApJ 795 45 35.
 36. Verde, L., Schöneberg, N., & Gil-Marín, H. (2023), arXiv:2311.13305
 37. Wong K. C., Suyu S. H., Chen G. C. F. et al (2020). H0LiCOW – XIII. A 2.4 per cent measurement of H0 from lensed quasars: 5.3σ tension between early- and late Universe probes. MNRAS 498 1420.
 38. Mark Kamionkowski & Adam G. Riess (2022). The Hubble Tension Energy. arXiv: 2211.04492 (astro-ph).
 39. Jian-Ping Hu & Fa-Yin Wang (2023). Hubble Tension: The Evidence of New Physics. Universe 9: 94.

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